

PHYSICAL OF STUDENTS OF UNIVERSAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS INCREASE ENDURANCE

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Abstract: This thesis is about increasing the level of endurance of students of general education schools.

Key words: endurance, training, physiological principles, anaerobic endurance, running.

Achieving high results in physical education lessons can only be achieved through the proper organization of the lesson and the use of effective methods. Education of young people and acquisition of modern knowledge is one of the main goals of the educational system. It is important to organize physical education classes at a high level in general education schools and to increase the resilience of students. At present, it is widely accepted that the leading functions, which reflect qualitatively different types and levels of endurance, mean the energetic capabilities of the organism. The quality of endurance, at the same time, allows to evaluate the quality of training loads based on physiological signs, to determine and detail (study in detail) the methodology of training middle-distance runners. Based on physiological principles, taking into account physical exercises, it opens the way for a precise and differentiated registration of the used training tools according to the nature and level of their impact on the body. In recent years, when it comes to endurance, it can be observed that pedagogical and physiological concepts have merged. The concepts of aerobic and anaerobic endurance have entered our daily speech. Sports activities requiring types of endurance do not clearly reveal the direction of impact, so now endurance is also classified into subtypes. Thus aerobic endurance is divided into short-term, aerobic, medium and long aerobic endurance. The first of these includes 3-10 minutes of physical exertion, the second includes 10 to 30 minutes of physical exertion, and the third includes physical exertion lasting more than 30 minutes. According to this classification, 1500 m. Running is a type of short-term aerobic endurance. Anaerobic endurance is the same: it is divided into short-term, medium-term and long-term types. To the first of these, running at the highest speed for up to 20 seconds (distances up to 200 m.), to the second – 60 up to a second, and the third - up to 3 minutes of running. Exercises aimed at the development of endurance have a physiological, biochemical effect on the functional state of the body of sportsmen. and causes other changes; the metabolism and oxygen consumption in the lungs increases, the volume of blood during the pulse and in the minute, the amount of lactic acid increases. It has been shown that a slow and scientific approach should be taken in the education of endurance in children and adolescents, taking into account the slowness of the functional readiness of the organism, and at this age it is necessary to educate the qualities of agility. According to some scientists, extreme caution in the development of endurance confirms that school-aged children have not been given full physical training. In addition to this, running is mainly used as a means of physical education in the education of general endurance at the adolescent age; our scientists suggested replacing long-distance running again with general development exercises and breathing exercises. Schoolchildren can overcome fatigue in a short time due to a small stagnation of stimulants of the nervous system. When training endurance in children of junior

school age, it is necessary to perform exercises of lower than average and variable intensity, which make great demands on the aerobic-glycolytic capacity of the body. When continuous exercise lasts more than 2 minutes and the intensity is around 50% of the maximum, the most effective tool at the age of 11-12 years is 2.7 m/s, at the age of 12-13 years at a speed of 2.8 m/s, at the age of 13-14 years 3 It runs at a speed of 06 m/s and lasts more than 10-15 minutes. Rest is 3-5 minutes. If in long-distance running, if the exercises last around 65% of the maximum, at the age of 11-12, the intensity is set at a speed of 3.1051 m/s, the duration of the exercises is up to 3-15 minutes, and the rest is up to 4-6 minutes. In the development of endurance, general endurance exercises are best developed gradually, up to 15-20 minutes. In adolescents, the main outcome of general endurance, maximal oxygen uptake is the main indicator of work capacity. Muscles performing exercises at high intensity do not reach the level of oxygen demand. In anaerobic processes with a high load intensity, exercises last a few seconds. In conclusion, it can be said that in the process of organizing physical education classes with students of general education schools, it is important to develop the physical potential of the student and increase the level of endurance. In this case, it is appropriate to pay more attention to the activities conducted with students.

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